

On the Distribution of Energy in the Emission Spectrum of a Black Body; by Willy Wien.

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Abstract

This article is a faithful translation of Willy Wien's original publication from 1896: "*Ueber die Energievertheilung im Emissionsspectrum eines schwarzen Körpers; von Willy Wien.*" where he states its distribution law that experiment does not confirm for long wavelength. He states that radiation intensity is inversely proportional to the fifth power of wavelength and a function of temperature and wavelength.

No translation found on the Internet respects the original form. We offer this translated version for students or amateurs wishing to understand or discover the origins of Planck's law and Quantum physics.

2. On the Distribution of Energy in the Emission Spectrum of a Black Body;

by Willy Wien.^[1]

While the change in the heat radiation of a black body and its distribution over the individual wavelengths with temperature can be derived based on the electromagnetic light theory in a purely thermodynamic way without the aid of particular hypotheses, this has not yet been possible for the energy distribution itself. Nevertheless, it is like things that the dependence of the intensity on the wavelength should be completely determinable through the properties of the radiation itself because it only depends on the temperature and not on the unique properties of individual bodies.

The radiation of a black body corresponds to the state of thermal equilibrium and, as a result, to a maximum of entropy. For example, if one knows some process through which one could effect a change in the wavelengths in a known manner without any effort and absorption in the sense of an increase in entropy, then the distribution of energy in the spectrum of a black body would result from the condition of the maximum the entropy can be completely determined. Although, as one has shown in earlier work, the entropy of radiation of known intensity and color can always be specified, there are currently no visible physical processes through which a transformation of the color such as that required is evident. Therefore, it is only possible to determine the energy distribution with hypotheses.

E. v. Lommel¹⁾ and W. Michelson²⁾ attempted to base a complete radiation law on certain assumptions. The latter makes the following requirements:

1) E.v. Lommel, Wied. Ann. 3 p. 251. 1877.

2) W. Michelson, Journ. of phys. (2) 6. 1887.

1. Maxwell's law of the distribution of velocities among a large number of molecules is also valid for solid bodies.

2. The period of oscillation τ excited by a molecule is related to its progressive speed v by the following equation where ρ denotes a constant. (One obtains this assumption through a specific idea about the nature of the excitation of the radiation.):

$$\tau = \frac{4\rho}{v}$$

3. The intensity of the radiation emitted by a molecule is proportional to the number of molecules with the same oscillation period, an undetermined function of temperature, and an equally unknown function of living force, which further assumes a power of v^2 gives a limit.

The law that Michelson obtains from these assumptions results in λ_m Wavelength of maximum energy if ϑ denotes the absolute temperature, it gives:

$$\lambda_m = \frac{\text{const.}}{\sqrt{\vartheta}}$$

Otherwise, this law leaves the total emission as a function of temperature undetermined.

One has now tried to use Michelson's happy idea of using Maxwell's law of the distribution of velocities as the basis of the radiation law. However, the number of hypotheses that have arisen in this area because of our complete ignorance of the excitation of the Radiation is particularly uncertain by using the results one obtains like Boltzmann using purely thermodynamic methods.

The remaining hypotheses still leave uncertainty in the theoretical justification but offer the advantage that the results can be compared directly and extensively with experience.

Therefore, confirmation or refutation through experience will also determine the correctness or incorrectness of the hypotheses and will be helpful for further expansion of molecular theory.

The theorem that the radiation of a black body is present in an empty space surrounded by walls of the same temperature also applies if the radiation emanates from gases that come from the cavity through transparent walls from the outside through reflective walls. However, the gases must have a finite absorption capacity for all wavelengths. There is no doubt that there are gases that emit heat rays simply by increasing the temperature, such as carbonic acid and water vapor.¹⁾ One can treat highly superheated vapors as gases, and a gas mixture can always be produced by appropriately mixing different substances with a finite absorption capacity for all wavelengths. However, one should not consider the radiation the gases emit under the influence of electrical or chemical processes.

If one assumes that the radiating body is a gas, then Maxwell's law of the distribution of velocities will apply if one follows the kinetic gas theory. The absolute temperature will be proportional to the average vital force of the gas molecule. This assumption has acquired a high degree of probability through the work of Clausius²⁾ and Boltzmann³⁾ and is supported by Helmholtz's investigations into monocyclic systems, according to which both the living force and the absolute temperature have the property being the integrating denominator of the differential of the supplied energy is further supported.

To avoid the unnecessary complexity that would arise from introducing the various components of the gas mixture, let us imagine the mixture such that a component of the gas mixture preferably emits the homogeneous radiation under consideration.

1) Paschen, *Repeat. Ann.* 50. p. 409. 1893.

2) Clausius, *Pogg. Ann.* 142. p. 433. 1871

3) Boltzmann, *Wien. Ber.* (2) 53. p. 195. 1866.

4) Helmholtz, *Ges. Abh.* 3. p. 119.

The number of molecules whose speed is between v and $v + dv$ is proportional to the size given by:

$$v^2 e^{-\frac{v^2}{\alpha^2}} dv$$

Where α is a constant determined by the average speed v , which one expresses using the equation:

$$v^2 = \frac{3}{2}\alpha^2$$

So, the absolute temperature is proportional to α^2 .

The vibrations a molecule emits at its speed are utterly unknown in their dependence on its state. The generally accepted view is that the electrical charges of the molecules can excite electromagnetic waves.

We hypothesize that each molecule emits vibrations of a wavelength that depends only on the speed of the moving molecule and whose intensity is a function of this speed.

One can arrive at this conclusion through various assumptions about the radiation process. However, since such assumptions are currently wholly arbitrary, it seems safest to make the necessary hypothesis as simple and general as possible.

Since the wavelength λ of the radiation emitted by a molecule is a function of v , then v is also a function of λ .

The intensity φ_λ of the radiation whose wavelength lies between λ and $\lambda + d\lambda$ is, therefore, proportional to

1. the number of molecules that emit oscillations in this period,
2. a function of speed v , also a function of λ Where F and f are two unknown functions, and ϑ denotes the absolute temperature

Accordingly is:

$$\varphi_\lambda = F(\lambda)e^{-\frac{f(\lambda)}{\vartheta}}$$

Now, the change in radiation with temperature follows that of Boltzmann¹⁾ and me²⁾ given theory consists of an increase in the total energy in proportion to the fourth power of the absolute temperature and a change in the wavelength of each between λ and $\lambda + d\lambda$ enclosed energy quantum in the sense that the associated wavelength changes inversely proportional to the absolute temperature. If one imagines the energy at a temperature plotted as a function of the wavelength, this curve would remain unchanged at a changed temperature if the scale of the drawing were changed so that the ordinates were in the ratio $1/\vartheta^4$ reduced in size and the abscissions were in proportion ϑ enlarged. The latter is our value φ_λ only possible if in exponent λ and ϑ only occur as product $\lambda\vartheta$. If c denotes a constant, that is to set:

$$\frac{f(\lambda)}{\vartheta} = \frac{c}{\lambda\vartheta}$$

The increase in total energy determines the value of $F(\lambda)$. It has to be that way:

$$\int_0^{\infty} F(\lambda) e^{-\frac{c}{\lambda\vartheta}} d\lambda = \text{const. } \vartheta^4$$

$F(\lambda)$ can be determined using the method of indeterminate coefficients. We imagine $F(\lambda)$ developed in a series and set $\lambda = c/y\vartheta$, so it becomes as follows:

$$F(\lambda) = F\left(\frac{c}{y\vartheta}\right) = \alpha_0 + \alpha_{+1} \frac{\vartheta y}{c} + \alpha_{+2} \frac{\vartheta^2 y^2}{c^2} + \dots + \alpha_n \frac{\vartheta^n y^n}{c^n} + \dots$$

$$+ \alpha_{-1} \frac{c}{\vartheta y} + \alpha_{-2} \frac{c^2}{\vartheta^2 y^2} + \dots + \alpha_{-n} \frac{\vartheta^{-n} y^{-n}}{c^{-n}}$$

1) Boltzmann, Wied. Ann. 22. p. 291. 1884.

2) W. Vienna, Ber. d. Berl. Acad. February 9, 1893.

The integration results:

$$\int_0^{\infty} F(\lambda) e^{-\frac{c}{\vartheta\lambda}} d\lambda = \frac{c}{\vartheta} \int_0^{\infty} F\left(\frac{c}{y\vartheta}\right) e^{-y \frac{dy}{y^2}} = \sum_n \alpha_n \frac{\vartheta^{n-1}}{c^{n-1}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y} y^{n-2} dy$$

So it should be:

$$\text{const. } \vartheta^4 = \sum_n \alpha_n \frac{\vartheta^{n-1}}{c^{n-1}} \Gamma(n-1)$$

All coefficients are zero except one, which gives $n = 5$ by the following equation:

$$\vartheta^{n-1} = \vartheta^4$$

So here it is:

$$F(\lambda) = \frac{\text{const.}}{\lambda^5}$$

The equation for φ_λ is the following:

$$\varphi_\lambda = \frac{c}{\lambda^5} e^{-\frac{c}{\lambda\vartheta}}$$

From this, it follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\varphi}{d\lambda} &= -\frac{c e^{-\frac{c}{\lambda\vartheta}}}{\lambda^6} \left(5 - \frac{c}{\lambda\vartheta}\right) \\ \frac{d^2\varphi}{d\lambda^2} &= -\frac{c e^{-\frac{c}{\lambda\vartheta}}}{\lambda^7} \left(30 - \frac{12c}{\lambda\vartheta} + \frac{c^2}{\lambda^2\vartheta^2}\right) \\ \lambda = \frac{c}{5\vartheta} \quad \text{becomes} \quad \frac{d\varphi}{d\lambda} &= 0 \\ \frac{d^2\varphi}{d\lambda^2} &= -\frac{5c e^{-5}}{\lambda^7} \end{aligned}$$

$d^2\varphi/d\lambda^2$ is negative, so the value corresponds to a maximum. We want to denote this value by λ_m . The associated value of φ is:

$$\varphi_m = \frac{c}{\lambda_m^5} e^{-5}$$

Since both φ and $d\varphi/d\lambda$ for $\lambda = \infty$ disappear, the curve is an asymptote on the λ -Axe.

Furthermore, $d^2\varphi/d\lambda^2=0$ for the roots of the equation

$$30\lambda^2\vartheta^2 - 12c\lambda\vartheta + c^2 = 0,$$

so for

$$\lambda = \lambda_m \left(1 \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{6}}\right).$$

The curve has turning points for these two points. If one sets $\lambda=\lambda_m(1+\varepsilon)$, then it becomes:

$$\varphi_\lambda = \frac{C e^{-\frac{c}{\lambda_m(1+\varepsilon)\vartheta}}}{\lambda_m^5(1+\varepsilon)^5} = \frac{C e^{-\frac{5}{1+\varepsilon}}}{\lambda_m^5(1+\varepsilon)^5}$$

also

$$\log \frac{\varphi}{\varphi_m} = -5 \left(\log(1 + \varepsilon) - \frac{\varepsilon}{1+\varepsilon} \right) = -5 \left(\frac{1}{2}\varepsilon^2 - \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon^3 + \frac{3}{4}\varepsilon^4 \dots \right)$$

Let us put $-\varepsilon$ for ε , so is

$$\log \frac{\varphi}{\varphi_m} = -5 \left(\frac{1}{2}\varepsilon^2 + \frac{2}{3}\varepsilon^3 + \frac{3}{4}\varepsilon^4 \dots \right)$$

Here, the absolute value of the series is more extensive, i.e., φ/φ_m is smaller than with positive ε ; as long as $\varepsilon < 1$, the ordinates at the same distance from the maximum are smaller on the side of the small wavelengths.

In a previous work¹⁾, one deduced that a black body's energy curves at different temperatures should not intersect. From this, one could further deduce that the curve towards the side of the long waves must fall more slowly than the curve from this equation:

$$\frac{\text{const.}}{\lambda^5}$$

That is the case with our curve; $d\varphi_\lambda/d\lambda$ is always less than 5 in absolute value $5C/\lambda^6$ and only reaches this limit for $\vartheta = \infty$. For an infinitely increasing temperature, $\varphi_\lambda = C/\lambda^5$, and the maximum energy would approach the zero wavelength without restriction.

1) W. Wien, Wied. Ann. 52. p. 159. 1894.

When one derived the formula for φ_λ from the theoretical considerations mentioned, the formula was independent of Mr. Prof. PASCHEN

$$\varphi_\lambda = \frac{C}{\lambda^\alpha} e^{-\frac{c}{\lambda\theta}}$$

(where α is a constant) as the one that best reflects his observations. He was kind enough to let one know and share his formula here. Mr. Prof. Paschen intends the value of the constant α from the complete calculation and comparison of his observations. If α is not 5, then the total emission would not follow Stefan's law.

Charlottenburg, Juni 1896.

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Conflict of Interest:

The author declares no conflict of interest.

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References

[1] *Ueber die Energievertheilung im Emissionsspectrum eines schwarzen Körpers*; von Willy Wien.:

[http://myweb.rz.uni-augsburg.de/~eckern/adp/history/historic-papers/1896_294_662-669.pdf]

[<https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.18962940803>]